

Entrepreneurships within Small and Medium Enterprises: A study of Entrepreneurs' Motivation in Nepal and India

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Abstract: *Entrepreneurship is an old concept, even existing during the barter system. Entrepreneurship development was a concern of becoming resourceful. Entrepreneurship exists in various organizations, not alone from management. Entrepreneurship development requires various Skills, Abilities, Knowledge, Competencies, Intelligence, and Experimental Determination (SAKCIED) to bring about creative innovation, creative imitation for creative construction, and creative destruction. Entrepreneurship development requires a Felt-Positive need Motivation (FPM) from within, driven by emotional values, to serve, to gain social status, being rational as an economic man (homo economicus), acting differently, and continuing to contribute, requiring intensified drive of needs, which is essential. This study is a qualitative exploration of the intensified drive-need of entrepreneurs from Nepal and India. Seven respondents participated in this research. Open-ended interviews were conducted. Data triangulation analysis was applied, and crystallization methods were used to give subjective meaning. The results suggested that creative innovation and creative imitation may not always be effective in breaking traditional boundaries, but creative construction and creative destruction can have a high impact on breaking boundaries and win over the competitors. Creative construction and creative destruction may not be easily achieved. Leadership creative approaches towards developing of fast-moving essential products and socially highly valued products can bring about creative constructions of a new product or creative destruction of the existing product in the existing market. Creative leaders activate their actions-oriented behavior towards creative imitation and innovation, while some creative leadership approaches go beyond the expected actions-oriented behavior. These are directed by the leadership's need-based decision. These needs are engraved within the felt-positive motivation of an individual to dramatically bring about changes within the existing organization's internal and external environment. Therefore, creative leadership approaches towards breaking boundaries are the extreme determination of the entrepreneur's vision towards creative construction and destruction.*

Keywords: Creative imitation, creative innovation, creative construction, creative destruction, felt-positive need, motivation, empirical study, qualitative

Introduction

Entrepreneurship has an old history. Generally, entrepreneurship in olden days sprang up from the self-skilled professions and was applicable also during the barter system of economic management. Many developing countries, even today, are carrying out entrepreneurship through their self-skilled profession and producing goods and selling out to the local market, and these products are basically meant for household use. This generated a small income, which was also the main motivating factor towards entrepreneurship development because of the felt-positive need.

Nepal is culturally diverse and geographically diverse, being a landlocked country situated between the growing economies of China and India (Choe and Pradhan, 2010). A range of varieties cultural diversity within a country propagates these clusters of people to indulge into small self-made entrepreneurs of their own cultural products, which was then called handicrafts such as wooden products (masks, marionettes), clay products (vase, cooking utensils), bamboo products (nanglo, tuncha), musical instruments (Sarangi, madal), natural plant brooms (Kucho, jhadu), carpets (rugs), and painting (thanksa).

Similarly, in India, many people, especially in rural areas, are still motivated to use their professional skills to produce household items and sell them in the market that comes to daily use. These products can range from various aspects to handicrafts such as brooms, agricultural items, small rugs, sweets products, flower products. However, due to technological enhancement, many people have taken hype to install small machinery to produce it on a larger scale since the market in India is very big. Moreover, financial sectors in these related areas have also grown to support the small and medium enterprises that were also initiated by the government to some extent. These enhanced the development of small-scale entrepreneurship amongst the professionally skilled people.

Moreover, Nepal and India have cultural similarities in terms of religion and language scripts (Sharma and Thapa, 2013, p8) and the importance of collectivistic and close family ties (Rajbhandari, 2016).

Nevertheless, the products that are produced by the rural people both in Nepal and India were innovated and developed on the basis of their professions as the need for these products was felt necessary (Rajbhandari and Gurung, 2022). This motivated the buyers and the sellers to generate a felt-positive need to make a decision on consuming these household products in multiple ways, for example, usability, necessity, rationality, psychological efficiency and effectiveness, economy, etc.

Along the way, while the modernization was spread, these household products had different uses and were then sold as handicrafts to the local and foreign tourists. This then created an opportunity for the trading merchants to market and sell these goods in the tourist areas where the attraction of these goods was more admired by the foreign tourists.

While the descriptive history of manufacturing these products has a different meaning (which was need-based), in the 21st century, these products have now been able to reach every household both nationally and internationally as souvenir and gift items. Moreover, these local handmade innovative products have also been able to capture international businesses (Droege, 2021), where these goods are exported by the well-established trading enterprises by establishing a small-scale business by traders, later operated under the Small and Medium Enterprises (SME). However, the Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) that have innovated and are still producing these products are even now facing the problem of sustainability. One reason for this could be the rapid growth of development within the country, where most skilled people are changing their professions and seeking jobs both in the developed areas of the country and outside. Moreover, innovative technologies are now being introduced into the market and this have further dissolved the intention of manufacturing hand-made products such as, clay pot/vase are being replaced by plastics decorative vase/pots, a bamboo nanglo (which is still in use in all the Nepalese houses) are now being replaced by the plastic giving the same look and different shapes, natural brooms are also being replaced by plastics and rubber so and so forth (Rajbhandari and Gurung, 2022).

Although the new technologies have replaced the old method of producing goods, it has now felt necessary for the new mind to carry on with the old method of producing, which is generating the vibe of entrepreneurship. The new entrepreneurs are also well aware that they wouldn't be able to compete with technologies in producing larger quantities; however, the different mindset of using and utilizing the organic resources is now becoming increasingly important. This is due to the increase in unemployment and unsecured job placement caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (Khawli et al., 2022; Blustein et al., 2020). In addition, the felt-positive need motivations of reestablishing the hand-made products are also increasingly progressing due to the change in mindset of the new generation, who feel pride in using the national and local products for their existence.

During the 20th century, most Nepalese people were influenced by the “demonstration effect” (Gunesch, 2017) while imitating to purchase and use of technological products that were used in developed nations. While these technologically produced goods are not completely discarded, however, the felt-positive need to grow local entrepreneurs within a nation has created a niche market for these products, and it can grow big and even bigger in the future.

Entrepreneurship is not a new term in business; it was being practiced earlier by the merchants and traders, and it is still in practice today. However, the methods of presentations of undertaking the businesses in the modern era are different. Entrepreneurs cover innovations and imitations and creative construction as well as creative destruction (Agarwal, Audretsch, and Sarkar, 2008). The innovation and creations are instigated through the individuals SACKIED (Rajbhandari, 2022). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to reflect the entrepreneurship-creative innovation (C-Inv), creative imitations (C-Imt), creative constructions (C-Const), and creative destruction (C- Dstr) along with their felt-positive need to grow within the business environments of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME).

Theoretical constructions

While this study is designed to corroborate motivation and entrepreneurship development, a felt-positive need motivation, which is a “psychological and sociological attachment of an individual’s” (Congshan, Yameng and Min, 2018; van Zomeren, 2013) need-based model, and is not mutually exclusive. The following theoretical construction was derived from the economic, psychology, social and management philosophy, which is further elaborated to construct into entrepreneurship philosophy.

- Need for emotional values (NEmv)
- Need of rationality as an economic man (NEco) (*John Stuart Mill as the “creator” of the economic man- homo economicus* (Bee and Desmarais-Tremblay, 2023),
- Need for gain (NGain)
- Need for serving, (NServe)
- Need for differences (NDiff)
- Need for Continuation and Contributions (NCont/Cntrb)

Figure 1: Felt-Positive Need Motivation (FPM)

Need for emotional values (NEmv) is the individual's need for felt-positive motivation to remain patriotic within the nation and have emotional value for the nation's products. The more emotionally attached an individual is to the nation's products, the intense drive to consume the national products is higher, and supposedly assuming the consumption of the national products contributes to the national economy. This need is an intense emotional driving force that attempts to corroborate felt-positive need motivation within the socio-psycho paradigm. A NEmv is a drive towards the emotional-motive need of an individual to create values towards deriving appreciative recognition.

Need of rationality as an economic man (NEco) is an individual's felt-positive need to economize the resources by up-cycling the under-utilized and unutilized resources. A NEco is a need to rationalize the resources through utility analysis for maximizing the uses of unutilized and under-utilized resources with a purposeful drive to minimize the cost and attempt to become a rational economic man.

Need for gain (NGain) is an individual's drive for felt-positive need to gain through return on involvement. This need can be both intrinsic and extrinsic. These intrinsic and extrinsic can be related to psychological need as well as sociological need. A NGain psychological gain can relieve the stress, while the social gain can be of affiliations and well-being.

Need for serving (NServe) is an individual's felt-positive need to serve for social causes. A NServe is a need to become socially responsible and serve as a person of need arises within an environment.

Need for differences (NDiff) is an individual inner felt-positive need towards demonstrating the methods of doing things differently to achieve higher returns and outcomes. A NDiff is a drive-need to demonstrative the creativity within the task/job. While most people are routinely performing the task/job, the NDiff needs crave for autonomy and feedback towards diversifying the methods for effectiveness at work.

Need for Continuation and Contributions (NCont/Cntrb) is an individual's felt-positive need of psychological drive towards contributing and supporting others and continuously performing to support as and when needed. NCont/Cntrb is a selfless continuous contribution towards society for seeking the welfare of the community, where everyone can have a quality of working life in a conducive environment and creating the possibility of a harmonious organizational climate and culture.

A conceptual design

A concept for this study was derived from the theoretical framework on the basis of interdisciplinary philosophy, which was further conceptualized and integrated into developing an entrepreneurship philosophy. The conceptual design is illustrated below in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework: Motivation and entrepreneurship development

A felt-positive need is a motivational drive that instigates entrepreneurs to delimit their boundaries for seeking the need for Need for emotional values (NEmv), Need of rationality as an economic man (NEco), Need for gain (NGain), Need for serving (NServe), Need for differences (NDiff), and or Need for Continuation and Contributions (NCont/Cntrb). This instigation of entrepreneurship development occurs through multiple variations further instigating them towards “creative-innovation, imitation” (Wierzbicki and Nowodziński, 2019) and creative-destructions and constructions. Both these motivational needs drive and entrepreneurial development have interconnectedness, which arises from inner drive towards agitating for the eruptions of their felt positive need.

Research Methods, Materials, and Mechanism techniques

This study is a qualitative analysis. For the collection of data, open-ended interviews were designed. The interview questionnaire was distributed among entrepreneurs operating small and medium enterprises in Nepal and India. The key respondents for this study consist of both male and female entrepreneurs operating various businesses. For this study, a total of seven respondents were selected on a random and convenient basis. An interview questionnaire was developed and distributed by email. The respondents for this study were identified from the professional community network, which assimilated different individuals. An open call was issued for participating in this study. There were altogether ten respondents who willingly accepted the invitation; however, only seven respondents’ interview questionnaires were collected for analysis.

The interview questionnaire was distributed to the respondents, and they were allowed a few days to return with their answers to the questions asked under the interview questionnaire. The interview questions were designed in two sections, interconnecting the felt-positive need for operating the enterprises and their creativity to expand the business for entrepreneurial development. Respondents from Nepal and India were given pseudonyms indicated after the respondent’s identity, Nep1, Nep2, Nep3, and Ind1, Ind2, Ind3, and Ind4.

The data were coded and further analyzed using the “data triangulation” (Turner and Turner, 2009) for content analysis (Guédé, 2022). These data were further processed through crystallization analysis (Rajbhandari, 2021; Stewart et al., 2017; Ellingson, 2009) by integrating their felt-positive need motivational and their entrepreneurial strategies within their businesses to further give meaning to support the theoretical construction and the conceptual design of this study.

Findings and Discussion

In this section, a data presentation is constructed to reflect the motivation, felt-positive need, and entrepreneurship development. The findings of this study are illustrated in line with the theoretical construction and conceptual design.

In relation to the felt-positive need motivation of an entrepreneur, the results suggest that all these needs are associated with their integrity and are felt positively by the respondents of Nepal and India. Although this study does not take a comparative study turn, it is, however, significant to illustrate the similarities between the two Asian based countries' entrepreneurs. In connection to the theoretical construction, entrepreneurs from India have a high degree of acceptance towards the Felt-Positive need Motivation (FPM). The results for the felt-positive need motivation of both countries are presented below in Table 1.

Table 1: Degree of acceptance for Felt-positive need motivation: India and Nepal

Felt-Positive Need Motivation (FPM)	Degree of acceptance	
	Nepal (Nep-1/2/3)	India (Ind-1/2/3/4)
Need for emotional values (NEmv)	Higher	Higher
Need for rationality as an economic man (NEco)	Average	Higher
Need for gain (NGain)	Average	Higher
Need for serving (NServe)	Higher	Higher
Need for differences (NDiff)	Average	Higher
Need for Continuation and Contributions (NCont/Cntrb)	Higher	Higher

Among the six components of Felt-Positive Need Motivation (FPM), respondents from Nepal have an average felt-positive need for NEco, NGain, and NDiff; however, the respondents from India have a higher degree of acceptance for all six components of Felt-Positive Need motivation.

The FPM is a driving element of entrepreneurs towards creative imitation and creative innovation. Without the creative imitation and creative innovation, creative destruction and creative construction are not possible, and without the four creativeness's entrepreneurship

development is not promising either. These creativenesses are closely interconnected with the FPM, which drives the motivation of the entrepreneurs towards innovative (unthinkable and unimaginable) endeavours.

The FPM agitates the mind of an entrepreneur towards thinking differently, which instigates the entrepreneur to generate the felt needs. However, the creative destruction or the creative construction may or may not last long. This is definitely the determining factor that lies within the acceptance level of customers or end users. Moreover, the FPM is guided by the philosophy of an entrepreneur's need-based decision, which is felt to be beneficial through the changes implied. The Felt-positive need is derived from the conceptual design and is further developed towards entrepreneurship development through the findings of this study within the felt-positive need motivation and entrepreneurship philosophy.

Figure 3: Felt-Positive Need driving entrepreneurial development

Need for emotional values (NEmv)

Within the Felt-positive need, an emotional value for the nation's growth is of great concern. Entrepreneurs' motivation towards creative innovation or creative imitation (Wierzbicki and Nowodźński, 2019) can have a positive cause-and-effect relationship. This can either have the causative effects on creative destruction of the available products in the market or can have the causative effects of creative construction towards developing a newly introduced product of its own kind. Entrepreneurs' motivations towards creating emotional values can be very intense for the initiatives they take for SME development. The respondent Nep1 mentions to reflect the encouraging emotional values for undertaking SME by saying

"I intent to carry the entrepreneurship through own experience, facing all challenge, taking all struggle as opportunity"

An intense motivation to initiate the SME through the emotional values can come from motive to compete for creative construction, which can impact the other product/SME, leading to creative destruction. In relation to the motive to compete globally with the entrepreneurs' innovation, respondent Nep2 says;

“As an entrepreneur, I intent to build a strong institution to compete with global business”

A felt-positive need for emotional values can generate creative innovation for their product and SME. These creative innovations may not only be related to product-based innovation but can also be positively related to some creative thoughts and actions, which can simultaneously be related to new idea generations for the product and the SME or towards the customers. In relation to this, Nep3 says;

“As an entrepreneur I have attached emotional feelings to the customer, using tools like country mascots, games, poet, landscapes, or charity. It's not so hard but you have to plan Smart”

Emotional values exist from the entrepreneur's thoughtful behaviour towards the customers and further to acquire their trust in return. Similarly, respondent Ind2 from India in regard to emotional values, says

“To understand your customers behaviours you first must understand their emotions. Behaviours are the consequence of emotions and emotions are the consequence of thought. We first need to build trust that we can surely provide better products made locally as compared to imported products and then need to ensure to maintain the quality and even work on to make it better”

In the same vein, respondent Ind3 indicates;

“promoting the benefits of it through word of mouth marketing and other available channels. How it creates employment opportunities. Getting to know about the global best practices which in turn are beneficial not only for the products but also for the entire industry”

Consequently, emotional values are generated from within an organization's internal environment. The Quality of Work Life (QWL) (Walton, 1973) and the internal human resources maintenance system of any organization need to be efficient and effective, while utilizing the locally available resources that identify the local essence. Respondent Ind1 mentions;

As an entrepreneur, I would promote all labor, procurement of raw materials and consumables locally and add to the local development, thereby keeping me more and more emotionally inclined to my region

The human resources maintenance factors offer employees' well-being, if the maintenance factors can assimilate the Psychology, Sociology, and Physiology (PSP) parameters that eventually benefit the organizational quality of working life (Rajbhandari, 2015).

Respondent Ind1 further extended his motives to expand the emotional values with the capacity of entrepreneurship, for which he says;

“My efforts of local produce give an opportunity of employment to the people of my vicinity, promotes local trade, taxes paid are returned by way of local infrastructure development and above all good work is appreciated by the mass in form of regard and social recognition in return”

Respondent Ind2 adds to support by saying;

“I am contributing towards growth of my country and helping people by creating jobs and opportunity to grow, also by finding additional meaning in the product beyond the function described in the specification of the catalogue”

Emotional values are attached to incorporate the growth of the nation as a whole through small contributions from the nation's people. Entrepreneurship for their creativity to feel the importance of the contribution that they have made as a nation's citizenship, this can also be the way to illustrate an example towards generating creative imitation which other follows to pay attention to. In this connection, respondent Ind4 states

“Feel local, connected and being able to help people of my country where I am resident at and paying my taxes”

The need for emotional values is backed up by the entrepreneurs' felt-positive need. The feelings of contribution, either with creative innovation or creative imitation, are driven by intense motives of an entrepreneur. These emotional values for the contribution of services or products are particularly directed towards the directed goal of the nation's development. Although a contribution could be at the micro level but the impact on the growth of the national economy can be felt with the initiation of entrepreneurship motives to drive the innovation further, which could be through creative construction or creative destruction.

Need of rationality as an economic man (homo economicus) (NEco)

Resource mobilization is the ultimate rationality of felt-positive need to indicate an entrepreneur as an economic man. The systematic process of mobilizing the unutilized and under-utilized resources can prevent the overuse of resources and further manage to prevent excessive waste. The concept of recycling is surpassed by the concept of up-cycling waste resources and cutting down the excessive use of available resources. This felt-positive need for rationality as an economic man can bring about creative innovation and creative construction.

Felt-positive need for economic man does not relate alone with profitability; however, NEco can be a strategic option for crisis management. Moreover, crisis management at the national level is more important than managing the crisis of an organization; however, there is a reciprocity effect at the micro and macro levels. Respondent Ind2 mentions;

“We need lots of papers, so we use recycled papers from a vendor who is manufacturing locally and helps in protecting trees”

Adding up to support the views, respondent Ind2 says

“We use to give gifts to various departments which are manufactured locally in North-East, Himachal, Uttarakhand like hand-made baskets, shawls, etc. I personally prefer khadi shirts and ask my staff to try it as well. One always has an option to use local resource rationally before opting for an outside resource”

Moreover, within the state of mindfulness of entrepreneurs with the felt-positive need rationality as an economic man (NEco), mobilization of unused, unutilized, or under-utilized resources can somehow paralyze the need for quality. This may be due to a cut down in financial resources involved in the management and operational process. Nevertheless, within the NEco, if the quality is given priority, an entrepreneur can lead towards progressive development of the SME's with their innovative thoughts and ideas, which eventually can have an impact of creative construction or creative destruction. Entrepreneurs' skills and abilities play an important part in SME growth and survival (Amatori, 2006). However, creative construction or destruction is a post-feedback reflected on the products, ideas, and thoughts of an entrepreneur upon acceptance or decline to use the services or products by the customers. Moreover, marketing strategies can have a bigger impact to succeed in the existing market, given the circumstances of felt nationality.

Similarly, most respondents feel that quality should not be compromised but utilizing the locally available services and products to complement their own services or products can additionally boost the energy of other locally established manufacturers. Respondent Nep1 says regarding the quality of their services by stating;

“We priorities for Quality, so it depends how the Quality matters”

Towards promoting the locally established services and consuming the local products, and further creating the opportunity can be an entrepreneurial rationale to instigate to promote to mobilize the local resources, respondent Ind1

“I consider saving on the transportation costs in alignment with promotion of local trade and job opportunities. I persuade local suppliers to cater to my requirements, thereby giving them another opportunity to explore and excel”

Moreover, entrepreneurial ideas and thoughts play a vital role in the development process through various means, one of them is also education. Supporting this view, respondent Ind3

“We can have development by educating them, by imparting required skills and by making them confident in their work”

Although it seems theoretically possible to implement the idea of rationality into practical ground, the reality can be very different, and this can be due to various contextual settings or even differences in the availability of resources. Despite an entrepreneur's thoughts or idea to mobilization can be practically feasible to some extent, but in reality ground it can even be costlier, which thus may not reason for NEco as a felt-positive need. This can be one of the major reasons for ongoing under-utilization and utilization of existing resources. Respondent Nep2 supports this view by stating

“Except for human resources and available local resources, the potentiality of the availability of local resources has not been able to harness due to scalability and quality issues”

Although felt-positive need for rationality as an economic man seems to be an easy task for most entrepreneurship development, it is difficult to accumulate these components. This can be due to the reasons of availability, easy access, and the practicality of usability. While the internal environment may allow initiating this rationality behavior but the external environment can have some reservations and may not offer a valid reason for positive felt-need, but rather deflect a felt-negative need. This opposes the need for rationality as an economic man (NEco).

Need for gain (NGain)

Return on involvement is an absolute gain towards achieving the felt positive driven need. While the need for gain is mostly intrinsic, it can also bring about physical satisfaction by fulfilling the wants of society. Moreover, social entrepreneurs have an immense inclination towards achieving this need by somehow engaging themselves in the betterment of society. In return, this involvement is enriched with the return on involvement gained by raising the status in society. However, social entrepreneurs' actions require selfless contributions and towards gaining grounds on the positive self-interested parameters of leadership through positive Focus, Optimistic, Strive, and Smile (FOSS) (Rajbhandari, 2011). The Need for gain (NGain) is a powerful reflexive paradigmatic image that produces the mirror-effect of Psychological, Sociological, and Physiological (PSP) parameters (Rajbhandari, 2015), which can be both positive and negative of their undertaking.

NGain's behavioural PSP mirror-effect (Rajbhandari and Rajbhandari, 2015) of can be positive from the social welfare side, while the political gesture to gain something out of the self-centered contribution can be negatively reflected. The dire need for the political image can therefore have less contribution towards the social welfare; however, the contributions without having the NGain can offer some psychological relaxation to their mind by being supportive to the needy society. This is supported by the respondent Ind2, by stating

“Helping old age homes, orphans by meeting their necessities occasionally. Keeping checks on organizations which are taking aid from Govt. that they are doing their duties responsibly for which they are getting aid. Helping poor clients to get justice who can't pay for themselves. Our firm requests judges to get the cost imposed on opposite party be given to Delhi Legal Services, instead of us. Helping new advocated when they get stuck by educating them free of cost”

NGain, as it can be a powerful tool for self-promoting oneself. However, a true contribution is a reflection of good deeds towards the needy society without anticipating personal and professional NGain rather than psychological gain. Ind1 mentions by saying;

“Such my intention that I'm heading a public charitable trust engaged into rendering of medical services, free of cost to the deserving and providing aid to such scholars in need of support for their education by sponsoring their academics”

Similarly, the NGain is recognition of one's doing good for society as a social entrepreneur. Respondent Nep1 says;

“Several contributions have been made by me which has brought inner peace and relaxation knowing I have done something for the society as bet as I can. Through our foundation, our team has worked extensively in the local community towards the betterment in health and education”

The NGain is a psychological achievement that offers peace and mindfulness to the contributors. In this connection, Nep3 replies to becoming mindful of his support;

“we support Orphan Care Nepal and Maa Samuha, but every little contribution helps, you feel relaxed when you see smile in their face”

The same views are shared by Ind4 by saying

“purely emotional but I always feel happy and 'gained' if I have been able to make a difference to the society – mostly monetary contribution but also some time and physical contribution. There comes a sense of achievement and content by seeing someone happy or better”

Some of the support from the entrepreneurs can be highly remarkable, which specifically has a cause for service and support, for example health-related issues, which can be costly and unaffordable. Respondent Ind3 claims that their support for the helpless has gained their recognition, he states.

“we have dedicated towards imparting education to the underprivileged and needy. Donations and contributions for various causes like unaffordable medical expenses and natural calamities”

Moreover, one of the aspects of entrepreneurs’ development can come through with the selfless services rendered to society, with the need of all kinds. Although entrepreneurs are different from middle-level managers’ intrapreneurs (Bosma, Stam and Wennekers, 2010), they can have a high capacity for development. Thus, utilizing these capacities can bring about NGain to the entrepreneurs and offer psychological relaxation by becoming mindful.

Need for serve (NServe)

Serving the nation through the lens of entrepreneurship is an enduring task. However, it is an obligation of every organization, if not the entrepreneurs, to become socially responsible towards their society and community. Nevertheless, few entrepreneurs go beyond the boundaries to serve the individuals and the community. This is an initiative taken by an entrepreneur for the need to serve others for a better society. The willingness to serve is a driven phenomenon that generates from within the inner belief to create social values; this is again driven by a need to serve (NServe) with a specific mindset of mindfulness, wellness, and wellbeing for individuals and for the community. Additionally, NServe is also the driving force for becoming socially responsible towards the betterment of society and community where an organization collides and coincides on an operational daily basis. However, the NServe attitude is found in a few entrepreneurs but is claimed by many to have been obliged towards serving society. Moreover, motivational emotions are a dire igniter for developing the attitude of becoming socially responsible and broadening the values for the need to serve.

Need for serve (NServe) is driven by the intensified felt-positive need for social obligation towards social responsibility. Supporting this view, Nep2 mentions,

“We are trying for sustainabile development and building capacity for community despite being a hugely loss making unit”

NServe is a drive that initiates from within an individual. This drive has an intensity to act on behalf of taking responsibility towards helping needy individuals, groups, and the community. This is supported by the respondents, as Ind2 mentions,

“Helped to settle in main stream of society and helped them in being responsible. Helped many people and families in settling their disputes out of professional lives through mediation and counselling. Helped the local-residents and market associations in getting rid of garbage dumps in locality through court order and helped municipality in getting a space where they can build proper structure for storing the garbage dump at one place. Helped several foreign nationals who are residing illegally and not getting proper facility by providing them assistance and bringing this in the knowledge of Human Rights Commission, so that they can be treated as humans till their deportation”.

Similarly, respondent Nep1 also supports the view of NServe as an intensified driven obligation by stating that,

“We have hosted several health camps and has always put a foot towards helping the needy people with things such as clothes drive, food drive. In the education area we have conducted numerous training and skill based programs for all, we have also been helping the students which need financial aid with various scholarship opportunities”.

Ind3 agrees towards the need to serve (NServe) as to help and support needy individuals, for which a felt-positive need-driven (NGain) is activated through an intensified motivation to become socially responsible towards the needy people (NServe), for which he states,

“We have served needy people by educating and meal distribution”.

Although Need for Serve (NServe) desire for everyone may not be the same, it can differ according to individuals and organizational motives. Some individuals and organizations can go even further to support and serve the community, which is an intense drive for a felt-positive need. This intensified drive for felt-positive need can come from an experience or through adequate acquisition of earnings during the period of establishment. Nevertheless, there are examples in history - during the war and crisis, a few people and organizations have served their community and country, becoming selfless towards human welfare. Moreover, in business and organizations, NServe could also be executed for gaining recognition in society and around the world, for which an additional value is added towards themselves and the organization. This is also a creative way to represent an entrepreneurial style in the modern era. However, most people and organizations driven for NServe are initiated for non-monetary gain, for which a respondent Ind4 states,

“Everyone plays their part and my organization current and in past have played their part as part of CSR by doing a lot of activities in helping others. Too many to list but none of them was done for monetary benefit”.

Furthermore, Felt-Positive need Motivation (FPM), for NServe is generated within oneself, which can be intensified as to need to serve or to gain from serving; however, during these services provided and offered, a monetary gain is nominal or nonexistent. However, NServe can thus generate a value-based identity by becoming socially obligated towards society.

Need for differences (NDiff)

Differentiation and diversity have become core components in today’s organization. Differentiation in multiple ways can exhibit organizational profitability, while it also illustrates entrepreneurialism productivity. Diversity and management can have a positive impact on the growth of entrepreneurship development by clustering different groups into one community. Moreover, within this differentiation and diversification, a Need for Difference (NDiff) can

agitate the existing business organizational external environment. The Need for Differences is a felt-positive need to exhibit the managerial style, doing it differently, but not doing a completely different thing. NDiff is essential to instigate innovative management processes and creative managerial style in the 21st century, which leads to both profitability and productivity of an organization.

All individuals are different, and there are a few entrepreneurs who do the same thing differently but avoid doing completely different things. A modern technologically equipped environment with the introduction of Artificial Intelligence (AI) within the “4th generation’s and rights of future generations (Cornescu, 2009) and “5th generation Cellular technology and human rights” (Bučiūnas, 2019) and the Artificial Intelligence and the Human Intelligence Mind (HIM) has even craved the entrepreneurs to think differently to shape organizational culture and climate (Rajbhandari, 2025). This has further instigated all entrepreneurs to think and act differently. There are very few things in this world to be innovated and invented, but the NDiff triggers to discover new ways to action-oriented behavior towards the community and within their own organizations. These NDiff can differentiate a growing industry from a stagnant organization, where the sustainability or existence of an organization can be in question matrix.

The importance of the Need for Difference (NDiff) in managerial style can have a lasting impact on the organization while making it different from other organizations in a competitive situation. The NDiff is also a felt-positive need motivation (FPM) driven by actions towards entrepreneurial success globally and being effective within an organization. NDiff-FPM enhances entrepreneurial creative innovation, creative imitation, and furthermore towards creative destruction and creative construction, thus developing the next level entrepreneurship for the 4th and 5th future generations.

Regarding the importance of NDiff in the 21st century, respondent Ind1 admits that

“Optimum utilization of man, machine and money (3M) and least wastage. I believe control and savings on the wastage is the first step of earning; one should focus and align in line with the requirements of one’s business, own management skills and customer satisfaction”.

Similarly, Nep2 admits that NDiff is necessary to stand out and to compete without resources,

“Being a Nepali manufacturing unit, we cannot compete in costs. But with differentiation it is possible”.

Getting things done differently can enhance entrepreneurial potential to remain effective and successful. Supporting this view, Ind2 states that

“We don’t manage people in the name of strict protocol and company policies, instead it’s a friendly atmosphere. We believe in hassle free approach and help at the time of need is appreciated. At times when an employ out of turn needs money he simply need to approach

finance and give in writing the nature of urgency and can take double of his salary in advance without any approval from manager or boss, etc.”.

Getting things done differently requires the managerial actions of doing things differently, for which Ind2 mentions,

“Instead of giving strict and traditional environment we try to keep it light and stress free ensuring that we do not miss the guide lines. Instead of sitting on head for work we educated our staff that they might be asked to pay the cost if it is imposed by court because of their lacuna, this keeps staff up on their heels and keeps them serious towards work”.

Doing things differently apparently differentiates the organization from others. Therefore, the remaining difference for others to succeed in a 21st-century competitive world, NDiff – FPM needs to be activated within every entrepreneur for a different level of actions-orientations towards their followers both within and outside the organization.

Nep1 states her view by saying,

“Our organization closely follows the SWOT analysis technique which has brought overall benefit to the organization and its employees. The SWOT analysis method consists of building a framework or a plan by analyzing the strength, weakness, opportunities and threats of the company. In my opinion this management style includes all the considerations and expectations of the people. In the 21st century it is essential to evolve our strategies and approaches to efficiently run the business. To be different and try new things will transform the business and will aid in reaching new heights which will ultimately beneficial for all sectors”.

Similarly, a respondent Ind3 also supports this view by stating,

“People first, empowerment, faith and trust in the workers. This all leads to alignment towards the company vision (s) to get excellent results because rapid technological advancements are happening in the new century and thus need to create a balance between the present and futuristic vision (s)”.

On the same line, Ind4 also has the same views to share concerning action-orientation towards followers for getting the things done differently, he mentions,

“Focus on people and everything people – their needs, behavior and wellbeing and business falls into place. Things are changing fast – I believe it has become even more important to retain the human touch and humanity given the technical advancements actually separating people more than ever”.

Respondent from Ind2 supports the view of action-orientation towards followers by stating,

“Out of the box thinking is required, as today unlike in past, cut throat competition in every field exists and it is taking pace on each passing day. People are becoming smart and smart is

becoming smarter. Technology is making difference in every field, new generation is adaptive to it and coming generation will born with technology, now it is not only important but its rather a dire need or requirement to get out of flock of sheep and start your own line which only possible if you are looking different”.

Nevertheless, NDiff is an essential component of entrepreneurship development, and this NDiff – FPM can represent the entrepreneurial creativity that can be demonstrated within their followership domain, where multi-flex leadership styles need to be demonstrated by a leader to acquire a leadership within and outside the organization (Rajbhandari, 2022).

Need for Continuation and Contributions (NCont/Cntrb)

Action orientation of an entrepreneur towards continuously contributing to the wellness and well-being of people within a society is a psychological drive which can intensify the NCont/Cntrb felt-positive need to support others and create a harmonious organizational culture and climate.

NCont/Cntrb is also a psychological drive for a social cause, which derives psychological satisfaction, thus enhancing entrepreneurship development and growth. NCont/Cntrb depends on the resources and capacity; however, some types of contributions and continuing them for a prolonged tenure is a determination that is implanted within an entrepreneurs. While resourcefulness is concerned with the drive for NCont/Cntrb, an entrepreneur must also acquire the inbuilt resources which are Skills, Ability, Knowledge, Competencies and Intelligences (SAKCI) (Rajbhandari, 2020) to exhibit the NCont/Cntrb. Within these SAKCI a determination to exhibit and execute it through experimenting with the contribution of these inbuilt resources, which then enables to evaluation of the entrepreneurs real Skills, Ability, Knowledge, Competencies, and Intelligences with experimental Determination (SAKCI-ED) (Rajbhandari, 2022).

In connection with SAKCI-ED, respondent Ind1 mentions the experimental determination of SAKCI by stating,

“My late grandfather, who was a philanthropist, such that he settled forming a charitable trust with the monetary gains he acquired more than his expectation, with the thought that this extra income may spoil his children, if taken home. Hence, he invested the money for a social cause, for the upliftment and betterment of the people of his region of domicile, working thousands of miles away from his own hometown. Since I was too much attached with him ever since as a child, I adopted and incorporated his thoughts in my own character and am following his footsteps and nurturing his dreams by leading his creation”.

There are multiple psychological concerns in motivating towards NCont/Cntrb. These psychological concerns may not be monetarily calculated but rather a subjective paradigm. Moreover, within NCont/Cntrb as an FPM, both recipients and the providers gain the psychological satisfaction through socially participating to support and help others with selfless

benefits. Furthermore, the psychological benefit acquired through NCont/Cntrb can have immense contentment within oneself. Supporting this view, respondents from both India and Nepal share their feelings and opinion regarding the NCont/Cntrb-FPM. They continue to state, accordingly, respondent Ind4 says,

“I feel relieved, content and a sense of achievement if someone is in better position than before because of me – be it anything. I feel happy, an eternal and internal satisfaction, feel worthy of being in this world and feel blissful and blessed to be able to have been of anyone’s help”.

Similarly, Nep1 mentions the confidence to NCont/Cntrb-FPM is due to the feeling of dependency on others who require support, she mentions,

“I feel that I need to continue to contribute even there is no financial gain because many more are depended on me with their confidence and I will be as a leading role is to care and support them”.

When comparing monetary benefits with the psychological benefits, a high psychological satisfaction (Self-actualization) level of NCont/Cntrb-FPM is acquired. This is also supported by Ind2 by stating,

“Hardly matters if money is coming or not or what amount is coming, because when you feel happy in doing something for others it gives you peace and happiness which is important”.

Similarly, Ind3 explains how to gain higher psychological satisfaction through NCont/Cntrb-FPM by stating,

“We are a soul and will carry impressions with it, so create harmless and good impressions through help and contribution to people and society”.

Entrepreneurs’ development through NCont/Cntrb-FPM can have a lasting impression on society. There are multiple examples of entrepreneurs who are well known for their drive for NCont/Cntrb-FPM. This impression through the NCont/Cntrb-FPM can also boost the organizational image and acquire a reputation for social welfare towards the community, society, and within their organization. This, therefore, helps to develop an entrepreneur through the FEM of NCont/Cntrb.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship development depends on multiple factors, a great leadership approaches to generating motivation of felt-positive need to Need for emotional values (NEmv), Need of rationality as an economic man, (NEco), Need for gain, (NGain), Need for serving, (NServe), Need for differences (NDiff), and Need for Continuation and Contributions (NCont/Cntrb). These motivational needs are mutually exclusive; some entrepreneurs activate their action-oriented behavior within their organization, while some entrepreneurs go beyond the expected

service action orientations. These are all guided by the philosophy of the entrepreneur's need-based decision. Moreover, all these needs are looked at from the perspective of Felt-positive Motivation (FPM) of an individual as an entrepreneur and entrepreneurial development.

The FPM aims to drive the entrepreneurs' need-based decision initiatives for creative innovation (C-Inv) and creative imitations (C-Imt), which further instigate entrepreneurship development through creative destruction (C-Dstr) and creative construction (C-Const). However, creative destruction and creative construction may have a reflection on the entrepreneur's C-Inv and C-Imt.

Within the theoretical framework of motivation and entrepreneurship development, entrepreneurs' FPM is highly affected by the positive need drive towards emotions, economic gain, serving, differences, and continuation and contribution to the organization and outside. These FPM triggers for entrepreneurship development through the medium of bringing about C-Dstr and C-Const through the entrepreneurship C-Inv and C-Imt. Nevertheless, C-Dstr and C-Const have a reflexive outcome on the individual's motivational need-based decision of FPM and entrepreneurial actions orientation through C-Inv and C-Imt, which can have prolonged consequences within and outside the organization.

Furthermore, within the degree of acceptance for FPM in this study of India and Nepal, entrepreneurs' FPM were found to be higher in Indian entrepreneurs, while in the case of Nepalese entrepreneurs, most of the FPM were found to be average, specifically in the FPM category of NEco, NGain, and NDiff. While other FPM category NEmv, NServe and NCont.cntrb were found to be higher in the case of Nepalese entrepreneurs.

Although this study was based on the philosophy of Motivation and entrepreneurship development, a comparative analysis was not conducted, but to explore the relational approaches between motivations towards entrepreneurship development. Entrepreneurs' FPM can have a direct impact on the Creative Innovation (C-Inv) and Creative imitation (C-Imt). However, FPM may not have a direct or positive correlation with the Creative Destruction (C-Dstr) or Creative Construction (C-Const).

C-Dstr and C-Const are independently driven by the situational and contextual settings of the external environment, which may be difficult to change. However, entrepreneurs attempt to creatively destruct or construct the market through creative thinking to create a marketing environment for specific marketable products. Thus, C-Inv and C-Imt are an entrepreneur's independent internal strategic management, while C-Dstr and C-Const are constructed in the external environment where an entrepreneur may not have control to agitate. However, it is the creative, unique products that complement or substitute the existing market product that is developed through entrepreneurs' creativity may have a likely chance to agitate the market and bring about either creative construction or creative destruction within the market with the innovative products.

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